

Global Digital Elevation Models in Coastal Area Analyses

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Abstract: This paper provides an overview of global digital elevation models (DEMs) with a special focus on their applicability in coastal areas, particularly in the context of coastal flooding risk assessments. For the pilot area of Kaštela Bay, an elevation contour of 1.5 m above sea level was derived from various global DEMs and compared against a higher-accuracy reference contour derived from a national large-scale LiDAR dataset. In low-lying areas, specifically the mouth of the Jadro River, the 1.5 m elevation contour was additionally identified through conventional land surveying. The comparison highlights differences in the spatial representation of low-lying areas, demonstrating how identical elevation thresholds can result in markedly different spatial patterns depending on the data source. This analysis demonstrates the potential of global DEMs for large-scale analyses and examines their limitations when applied to low-relief coastal environments.

Keywords: DEM; flooding; LECZ; risk assessment; accuracy assessment.

1 Introduction

Coastal areas are home to 40% of the world's population, including 12 of the world's 15 largest cities (UNEP 2026). Urbanisation is happening more quickly on the coast than inland (Cosby et al. 2024), leading to increased pressure on coastal regions. The scale of the risk is highlighted by the estimate that 10% of the global population lives in low-lying coastal zones up to 10 m above sea level, covering 2% of the land area. In 2000, this was about 600 million people (McGranahan et al. 2007), and it is now estimated to be over 700 million.

Coastal flooding remains a known hazard that will increase with climate change. Sea level rise combined with heavy rainfall already leads to compound flooding in low-lying coastal regions, with the Mediterranean area among the most affected. The DIVA assessment of sea level rise in the Republic of Croatia (PAP/RAC 2015) shows that the highest number of people flooded per floodplain area will be in the Kaštela Bay. The DesirMED project (DesirMED 2024), funded under the Horizon Europe Programme, prioritizes Nature-based Solutions (NbS), innovative technologies and social practices to accelerate the transformation towards climate adaptation and resilience in the Mediterranean. Within the framework of this project, models for the characterisation of landscapes on climate resilience and climate risk profiles are being developed (Tzavella et al. 2026). In the first phase of the project, a preliminary vulnerability analysis of the Kaštela Bay area was performed. The flood risk maps produced by Hrvatske vode for 2019 and with water depth thresholds of < 0.5 m,

0.5 m - 1.5 m, 1.5 m - 2.5 m, and > 2.5 m were utilised (Hrvatske vode 2021). For modelling floods caused by high sea levels, a digital terrain model (DTM) was used (Hrvatske vode 2021). This paper explores the applicability of global elevation data for coastal flooding risk assessments, specifically the derivation of areas on land that is below 1.5 m elevation and is contiguous to the coastline. We refer to this area as 1.5-m low-elevation coastal zone (1.5-m LECZ). Elevation of 1.5 m was chosen as the lowest elevation threshold from those determined by Hrvatske vode that we expect can be reliably derived from global elevation data.

According to Guth et al. (2021), a digital elevation model (DEM) is a common name for various gridded products in which pixel values correspond to elevation. If these elevations are related to the topmost edges of objects on the surface of the earth, including vegetation and buildings, then this DEM is referred to as digital surface model (DSM) and if elevations of vegetation and buildings are reduced to the bare ground, then this type of DEM is called digital terrain model (DTM).

In the following sections, we first introduce DEMs that we used in this study and explain how the 1.5-m LECZ was derived from them. Then we compare the obtained results and give possible reasons for observed differences and finally we state the importance of accurate elevation data for reliable coastal flood risk assessment.

2 Materials and methods

In this study, we determined a total area of 1.5-m LECZ in the Kaštela Bay and the City of Split in Croatia (Figure 1). To determine 1.5-m LECZ, we used several global freely-available DEMs, namely SRTM (NASA 2015), ASTER (Abrams and Crippen 2019), AW3D30 (JAXA EORC 2024), Copernicus DEM (ESA and Airbus 2022), FABDEM (Hawker et al. 2022), DeltaDTM (Pronk et al. 2024), FathomDEM (Uhe et al. 2025), and GEDTM (Ho et al. 2025), all with a pixel size within the study area of approximately 22.5 m in east-west direction and 30.9 m in north-south direction. FABDEM, DeltaDTM, and FathomDEM are all generated from the Copernicus DEM, and GEDTM from both Copernicus DEM and AW3D30 DEM, with the aim to bring those DEMs closer to a DTM. All other analyzed DEMs can be considered as being closer to DSM than to DTM. However, it still makes sense to compare the accuracy of generation of 1.5-m LECZ delineation from all of them since, as Guth et al. (2025) suggest, algorithms for generating DTMs from DSMs are black boxes and can locally produce significantly inaccurate results. The main characteristics of these DEMs are listed in Table 1.

Additionally, as a higher-accuracy reference source of elevation data, we used a DTM provided by the State Geodetic Administration of Croatia (referred to as LiDAR

Figure 1. Study area (Kaštela Bay in Croatia) with 1.5-m LECZ derived from classified aerial LiDAR data. Historic core of the City of Trogir (area marked with 'A') is shown in a larger scale in Figure 3, while mouth of the Jadro River (area marked with 'B') is shown in Figure 4.

DTM) that is derived from aerial LiDAR scanning, has a pixel size of 1×1 m, and covers entire Croatia (Babić et al. 2022). All used global DEMs are georeferenced in EPSG:4326 geographic 2D coordinate reference system (CRS). LiDAR DTM is, on the other hand, georeferenced in the EPSG:3765 projected CRS. To make the comparison between the 1.5-m LECZ derived from global DEMs and the reference 1.5-m LECZ valid, we regrided LiDAR DTM to the same grid defined by the global DEMs in EPSG:4326 with averaging elevations to the coarser pixel size.

Elevations in LiDAR DTM are given in HVRS71 vertical CRS (EPSG:5610, Babić et al. 2022), while the corresponding documentation and scientific papers referenced in Table 1 indicate that elevations in SRTM, ASTER, and AW3D30 DEMs are given in the EGM96 vertical CRS (EPSG:5773) and Copernicus DEM and other Copernicus-DEM-derived DEMs express elevations in the EGM2008 vertical CRS (EPSG:3855). Reference surfaces (i.e., geoids) in these

vertical systems are different, which can thus have a significant influence on determining the 1.5-m LECZ. The reference surface of the HVRS71 is modeled with the HRG2009 geoid model (Bašić and Bjelotomić 2014), while the geoids for the EGM96 and EGM2008 CRSs are derived from the corresponding geopotential models (EGM96 and EGM2008). We used T7D application that implements T7D transformation model (Bašić 2009) to derive HRG2009 geoid undulations within the study area and GeoGRAV web-application (NGA 2026) to derive EGM96 and EGM2008 undulations. Differences between geoid undulations of HRG2009 and EGM96 models ranged from 0.91 to 1.29 m and differences between HRG2009 and EGM2008 ranged from 0.45 to 0.52 m within the study area. In both cases, EGM2008 and EGM96 geoid models were above the HRG2009 model. The magnitude of these differences is in line with findings of previous studies for territory of Croatia (Hećimović and Bašić 2003, Liker et al. 2010). By using

Table 1. Characteristics of global DEMs used for generating the 1.5-m LECZ.

DEM and reference	Data source	Acquisition period and data type	Vertical CRS
SRTM v3 (NASA 2015)	C-band and X-band SAR	2000, Int16	EGM96
ASTER v3 (Abrams and Crippen 2019)	Satellite optical stereo images	2000–2013, Int16	EGM96
AW3D30 v4.1 (JAXA EORC 2024)	Satellite optical stereo images	2006–2011, Int16	EGM96
Copernicus DEM, GLO-30, 2024_1 (ESA and Airbus 2022)	X-band SAR	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
FABDEM v1-2 (Hawker et al. 2022)	Derived from Copernicus DEM	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
DeltaDTM v1.1 (Pronk et al. 2024)	Derived from Copernicus DEM	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
FathomDEM v1.0 (Uhe et al. 2025)	Derived from Copernicus DEM	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
GEDTM v1.2 (Ho et al. 2025)	Derived from Copernicus and AW3D30 DEMs	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008

*SAR–synthetic aperture radar

calculated geoid undulation differences, we transformed elevations in all used global DEMs from EGM96 or EGM2008 to HRG2009 since it has a centimeter-level accuracy for the territory of Croatia (Bašić and Bjelotomić 2014).

After deriving the 1.5-m LECZ from these nine DEMs, we calculated their areas and used them for comparison. Furthermore, 1.5-m contour in the low-lying area of the mouth of the Jadro River (area marked with 'B' in Figure 1) was determined by conventional GNSS-based land surveying in order to validate 1.5-m LECZ derived from the LiDAR DTM.

3 Results

Figure 2 shows a graph with areas of the 1.5-m LECZ derived from global DEMs and from reference LiDAR DTM. It also shows percentages of difference between reference LiDAR-DTM-based area and global-DEMs-based areas. Deviations from the reference area are quite significant, ranging from approximately three and four times smaller

Figure 2. Comparison of 1.5-m LECZ areas obtained from various DEMs. Percentages on this graph were determined as share of difference between reference 1.5-m LECZ area (based on LiDAR DTM) and from other DEMs in reference 1.5-m LECZ area.

for ASTER- and GEDTM-based areas respectively, to almost two times larger for the SRTM-based area. Figure 3 shows the historic core of the City of Trogir and 1.5-m LECZ

Figure 3. Historic core of the City of Trogir (area marked with 'A' in Figure 1) and 1.5-m LECZ (colored in red) derived from various DEMs.

Figure 4. Mouth of the Jadro River (area marked with 'B' in Figure 1) with 1.5-m LECZs derived from the LiDAR DTM and 1.5-m contour acquired by conventional GNSS-based land surveying.

derived from various global DEMs and from higher accuracy reference LiDAR DTM (in the middle).

In Figure 4, the mouth of the Jadro River with 1.5-m LECZ derived from LiDAR DTM and 1.5-m contour acquired by conventional GNSS-based field surveying is visible. The 1.5m contour is not continuous due to some areas not being accessible, making field surveying inconvenient or not possible.

From Figure 4 it is evident that 1.5-m LECZ derived from the LiDAR DTM closely resembles with the 1.5-m contour, which supports the choice of LiDAR DTM as a reference data source for assessing accuracy of derivation of the 1.5-m LECZ from various global DEMs.

From the graph in Figure 2, it can be concluded that within the study area, AW3D30 and FathomDEM report the area of the 1.5-m LECZ that is the closest to the reference LiDAR-DTM-based area, with underestimation of area by 5% and 8% respectively. Only SRTM overestimates 1.5-m LECZ area, with significant 88% overestimation. All global-DEMs-based LECZ areas are lower than the reference area, suggesting that elevations in global DEMs are in general higher than the actual terrain elevations. This is expected since global DEMs are usually considered to be closer to DSM than to DTM. However, such a good performance of the AW3D30 was not expected. AW3D30 is generated from satellite optical stereo images, meaning it should include vegetation canopy height and report a lower LECZ area than DEMs that are based on SAR observations that can penetrate through vegetation to a certain level. A quick visual inspection suggests that AW3D30 overestimated 1.5-m LECZ in low-lying vegetated areas. The reason for this unexpected AW3D30-related result might be linked to some postprocessing step in its production workflow. However, no final conclusion can be given without further investigation. ASTER is also based on optical images and its significant 1.5-m LECZ underestimation is therefore expected. Significant overestimation of the SRTM-based 1.5-m LECZ is also unexpected and requires further investigation.

When comparing Copernicus DEM 1.5-m LECZ area and areas derived from other DEMs that are based on Copernicus DEM (Figure 2), FABDEM and especially FathomDEM seem to be successful in removing vegetation and building elevations from Copernicus DEM. On the other hand, the performance of DeltaDTM and GEDTM is lower in this regard. Since the analysis is performed on a relatively small geographical area, it might be possible that accuracy of DeltaDTM and GEDTM is locally lower than their overall accuracy.

In Figure 3, urbanized area is analyzed. In these types of areas, SAR-based and optical-images-based DEMs are expected to perform the same since both record elevations of building tops. Therefore, Figure 3 can be used to visually assess how successful the algorithms are in removing elevations of buildings from Copernicus DEM data. Conclusion is similar to that from Figure 2 – in FathomDEM and FABDEM building heights were successfully removed.

It should also be mentioned that besides DEM acquisition method, which most certainly has the greatest impact on

deriving LECZ, another source of deviation is different acquisition periods. LiDAR DTM was produced from data acquired at least 10 years after the acquisition of data used for producing analyzed global DEMs. Although we are not aware of any significant earth works within the study area, since it is a relatively small area, even small-scale land alterations can significantly contribute to the variability of analysis.

The significant differences in the extent of the 1.5-m LECZ (Figure 3) produced from various global DEMs, shift not only the estimated extent of the flooding area, but also the locations where resilience interventions, such as NbS, should be prioritized. Therefore, elevation data uncertainties should, in addition to other uncertainties (Hinkel et al. 2021), be incorporated in decision support tools for resilience planning, especially in low-lying areas such as Kaštela Bay, as elevation data uncertainty can drastically alter placement of the adaptation responses.

Figure 2. Comparison of 1.5-m LECZ areas obtained from various DEMs. Percentages on this graph were determined as share of difference between reference 1.5-m LECZ area (based on LiDAR DTM) and from other DEMs in reference 1.5-m LECZ area.

4 Conclusions

This study evaluated several global DEMs for estimating the extent of the 1.5-m LECZ in Kaštela Bay in Croatia. Total areas of AW3D30-, FathomDEM-, and FABDEM-derived LECZ showed the highest agreement with the area of reference LiDAR-DTM-derived LECZ, while LECZ areas derived from other DEMs significantly deviated. These differences emphasize the importance of elevation data uncertainties on estimating flooding exposure and locating appropriate adaptation measures. Future work on this topic should explore approaches for reducing and/or incorporating elevation data uncertainties in coastal flooding assessment.

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